

Role of News Media in Enhancing Voters' Engagement: A Literature Review based Study

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ABSTRACT

News media plays an arbiter job between the general population and another world. Holding public trust in explicit news media is the principal task since those who trust them will be set up to sit tight for their most recent variant. Media outline data to impact the public's convictions and mentalities. Different media types, including print media, present the perspectives outwardly world that causes us in framing and reshaping our assessment towards a specific issue. Thus, by keeping in view the importance of media in general and news media in particular, this article examined the role of news media in accelerating voters' engagement and decision-making in the electoral process. We randomly selected a sample of n= 50 articles investigating the role of news media in political communication and its impacts. Cited literature revealed that, despite political framing and partial representations, the role of media reporting is highly acknowledged. As a result, First, media content influences the acquisition of more information on a political phenomenon. In the second step, acquired media information is accompanied by emotional and attitudinal reactions. Thus, from the early day of mass media research, media platforms are considered as a source of information and communication for the audience. Besides, partisan politics also influence the media stakeholders to convey the desired political information and benefit from financial and others. Furthermore, we have discussed the study limitations and made the recommendations.

Keywords: News Media; Elections; Political Communication; Decision-making; Voting Decision-making

1. INTRODUCTION:

News media plays an arbiter job between the general population and another world. Holding public trust in explicit news media is the principal task since those who trust them will be set up to sit tight for their most recent variant. Indeed, news associations may utilize dependable sources to check whether a hurriedly arranged thing by a contender has any reality in it (Shu et al., 2017). As

Riaz, (2009) brings up the part of the middle person as what we think about the world is largely dependent on what the media choose to advise us. He expressed that "the consequence of this intervened perspective on the world is that the needs of the media firmly impact the needs of people in general; Elements conspicuous on the media plan become unmistakable in the public psyche." When elites talked, columnists tuned in and recorded the data, refined it, and gave it to general society for their utilization. The general population isn't adequately shrewd to understand confounded, policy-driven issues. Besides, people, in general, are excessively overcome with their everyday lives to think often about the complex public approach (Riaz, 2009). As in the words of Reeves, Chaffee, and Tims, "There is an understandable tendency to place more trust in information from news media, which are professionally organized to validate and edit their content, than in messages we hear from other people or draw from our memories." (Chaffee & Tims, 1982)

Similarly, media associations and media individuals decide the news things just as the need is given to specific issues. The press likewise reveals to us which topics are the prime ones among a lot of progressing issues. Because of restricted assets, individuals rely on broad communications to gain wanted data, from which they comprehend issues. According to (Berinsky & Kinder, 2006), media outline data to impact the public's convictions and mentalities. Different media types, including print media, present the perspectives outwardly world that causes us in framing and reshaping our assessment towards a specific issue. Thinking about this thought, the media can impact the general sentiment by setting the plan and organizing the news. All of an unexpected we have news associations incredible before springing up everywhere on the web getting out bogus word sabotaging the numerous believable news sources. Individuals are getting out bogus word data through web-based media destinations yet go to chapel each Sunday. These embarrassments are in it for the cash and not for trustworthiness and exemplary nature. It has defamed news-casting dependent on one-sided feelings on significant issues that we all incentive to the most noteworthy extent. News media relying upon how it is introduced can represent the deciding moment individuals. While the entirety of this has become the standard in our everyday lives, recollect, valid, and genuine news coverage will consistently be near. We should give gratitude to the news media (DellaVigna & Kaplan, 2007).

Thus, by keeping in view the importance of media in general and news media in particular, this article examined the role of news media in accelerating voters' engagement and decision-making in the electoral process. We adopted literature review approach and cited the relevant literature to further draw the results and conclusion. We have further divided this article into four sections as per the research rules to examined the problem statement in an empirical manner.

2. RESEARCH METHODS:

Literature review-based investigations help to provide a systematic and strong evidence on the study problem supported by the existing literature. Review studies are important as they provide an in-depth insights regarding the problem statement and also help the future researchers to conducted more empirical studies on the relevant study topic (Ali, 2020). Thus, the current research is also based on the literature review approach. We randomly selected a sample of $n= 50$ articles investigating the role of news media in political communication and its impacts. Notably, the articles are selected from Google Scholar and Directory of Open Research Journals (DOAJ) search by the keywords i.e., media and politics, media and political participation, media and political decision-making, and media and voters’ engagement. Moreover, according to the frequency of cited literature by year, we found that a majority of articles were published from 2011 to 2015 ($n= 13$ or 61.9%), $n= 6$ or 28.5% were published from 2006 to 2010, and $n= 1$ or 4.7% of articles were published between 200 to 2005, and 2016 to 2021. See **Figure 1** for the graphical illustrations of the articles by year:

Figure 1: Frequency of Articles by Year

Similarly, we also calculated the frequency of the cited literature by their study design. Results indicated that, a majority of articles ($n= 9$ or 42.8%) were based on cross-sectional design, $n= 8$ or 38.2% of articles were having longitudinal study designs, and only $n= 4$ or 19.0% of publications belonged to the “other” or mainly perspective, research review, research essays, and others. **Table 1** contains the frequencies of articles according to their study designs:

Table 1: Frequency of Cited Literature by the Study Design

Study Design	N	%
Cross-sectional	09	42.8%
Longitudinal	08	38.2%
Other	04	19.0%

Finally, we examined the cited literature according to their methodologies. Frequency calculation revealed that, most of the articles ($n= 9$ or 42.8%) were having quantitative methods, $n= 7$ or 33.3% were having qualitative methods, $n= 4$ or 19.0% were based on other methods, and $n=2$ or 9.5% of cited research is based on the mixed-method approaches. **Table 1** contains the frequencies of articles according to their methodology:

Table 2: Frequency of Cited Literature by the Methodology

Methodology	<i>N</i>	%
Quantitative	09	42.8%
Qualitative	07	33.3%
Mixed-method	02	9.5%
Other	04	19.0%

3. MEDIA AND VOTERS' ENGAGEMENT:

3.1 Media and Voters Engagement in the Electoral Process:

Today, due to increased mass media platforms, the number of political information is also increasing. This increased information is directly correlated with the increased number of voters. For instance, in 2004, more than 75 million United States population actively engaged in gathering political information through different media platforms. However, in 2000, only 29.0% of the population searched for political information through media resources (Larson, 2004).

Various studies focused on the influence of mass media on voters' political engagement during elections. In this regard, D. V. Dimitrova et al., (2011) also examined the effects of mass media on political information and knowledge during the elections. The researchers used the case study method and selected a sample of $n= 4.010$ respondents from Sweden. Results revealed that, although media had weakly influenced the political knowledge of the respondents, there was a strong, significant correlation between media content and audience political participation as Hellweg, (2011) cited the example of power of media platforms that motivated the American public to vote during the elections in 2008. She argued that Barack Obama and his political party greatly relied upon mass media platforms to start and run their campaign. Staying connected with the public, keeping them updated about the campaign messages, focusing on public welfare, and helping them to acknowledge the importance of their votes all helped them increase political participation among the public.

Furthermore, Gentzkow et al., (2011) examined the impacts of American newspapers on voters' political engagement from 1869 to 2004. The researchers used experimental approach and conducted the content analysis of $n= 3.913$ newspapers. Results showed that, partial newspapers' coverage directly affected their voting engagement. Those who perceived presidential elections as unfair did not show interest in casting their voting compared to the other individuals. The researchers concluded that news media play an important role in motivating the voters as Alexis de Tocqueville also considered media as a source of increasing political participation. Matthes

(2011) noted that media educate the public about the importance of their votes to strengthen the democratic process. By reporting about the election campaigns, media platforms also facilitate the public to raise their concerns and voice their opinion. Political parties communicate with the public, convey their message, and actively encourage them to participate in the electoral process. Burford, (2012) also investigated the impacts of mass media on voters' participation in the elections. The researchers used an exploratory approach and selected social media content posted by the Muslim Council of Britain (MCB) during December 2011. Findings revealed that many posts motivated the audience to participate and vote actively for the Muslim Council of Britain (MCB).

Likewise, Sokhan, (2014) investigated the impacts of mass media on motivating and reinforcing political participation during- the Cambodia elections in 2014. The researchers selected an exploratory design and gathered data by using structured questionnaires. Findings indicated that respondents widely considered mass media an influential source, which further motivated them to participate in the voting process practically. Gil de Zúñiga et al., (2014) considered reinforcing political participation as a joint effort of conventional and new media strategies. As newspapers, television, and radio deliver information, new media further motivate to share, receive and validate this information. This describes the multifunctional role of media platforms being as informers, motivators, and ensuring political participation. In this regard, Moeller et al., (2014) scrutinized the impacts of both traditional and new media on political activities and participation during the elections., The researchers used experimental design and selected a sample of $n= 729$ respondents from the Netherlands. Results revealed that newspaper reading was strongly influential in participating in the online political information obtaining and sharing process. Moreover, the researchers also found the internal efficacy of print media as a major determinant of enhanced political participation among the voters. Skoric et al. (2016) also analyzed the correlation between mass media usage and citizen engagement in the elections to validate this phenomenon further. The researchers selected a meta-analysis approach and selected a sample of $n= 22$ studies published from 2007 to 2016. Results revealed that media tend to impact social, political, and civic engagement among the citizens. The researchers also found a strong significant relationship between media dependency during the elections and increased political information among the audience.

3.2 News Media and Decision-Making:

Democratic societies facilitate the citizens to vote and select their desired candidates independently. However, the dominance of government institutions on mass media platforms indirectly influences the people's opinion and political decision-making process (Hobolt, 2006). Hobolt further analyzed how and to what extent media influenced people's decision-making during the referendum for Denmark's integration with European Union. The researchers used the case-study method and found that political parties indirectly controlled the media platform during the

referendum. Although their content and messages did not contain any direct messages, they all greatly emphasized integration and its perceived benefits. Here Chong & Druckman, (2007) considered framing as vexing the public opinion and manipulating them through media content. Media plans and execute framing by making minor or major changes in their messages aim at large changes in opinion and attitudes. Especially during elections, when the public has little interest in any particular political party, it resorts to media content to gain attention and persuade people to vote or select them. Moreover, we assume that media framing is an indication of political power and dominance. Especially during elections, political powers dominate media platforms and help them to frame the content to manipulate the people to make favorable voting decisions. Due to biased media content, people develop positive opinions and vote for their desired political parties (Entman, 2007).

In this regard, Popescu, (2007) examined whether external political organizations, including the government, influence the mass media content during elections. The researchers used a cross-sectional design and used close-ended questionnaire for data gathering purposes. Findings indicated that citizens find it easy to make the relevant decisions with the ease of access to information through news media. Here, framing as a result of political communication is important as the more people are aware of political proceedings, the more they tend to decide accordingly. To further validate this, Wani & Alone, (2014) cited the role of media., its impacts on selecting Narendra Modi in Indian elections. According to the authors, as media is comparatively more capable of directly communicating with the audience, conveying political information is easier today. During the Indian elections, BJP seemed dominant on all the media platforms, and the news was based on conflict frames. The frequent use of conflict frames and BJP's dominance over media platforms led to Narendra Modi's success in elections.

Chang, (2009) further examined the media framing of the biofuels phenomenon and its impacts on audience perceptions and attitudes towards the issue. The researcher selected an experimental approach and selected a sample of $n=3$ newspapers in Iowa State, the United States. The content analysis of the selected newspapers indicated that media frames directly influenced the audience's perceptions about the biofuel issue. As the focus of media coverage was more on highlighting the economic consequences, the people were also concerned about the negative economic outcomes.

Issue framing is important, and one of the most practice framing techniques directly correlates with motivated reasoning. When political elites dominate the media content, they aim to influence the public in every possible manner. Slothuus & de Vreese, (2010) further cited the example of media framing by stating that elites might get public attention and support by showing their everyday charity work as a fight against illiteracy, unemployment, and poverty.

Likewise, calling the competitor's rally propaganda, drama, or attention-seeking act can also lead people to perceive the rally as represented in media. Especially during elections, politicians and their parties are the center of debate for all, leading the public to depend on media for information,

exposure to framed representations, and affecting their voting decision (Slothuus & de Vreese, 2010).

According to Schemer et al., (2012), media frames are more effective when the people's experiences resonate with the framed narratives. Previous research widely witnessed a potential correlation between personal experiences and media framing. Schemer and his colleagues further scrutinized the impacts of media framing on people's voting decisions in Switzerland. The researchers used the case study method and selected a sample of $n= 1,251$ respondents for the panel survey. Results revealed a strong positive correlation between media framing and people's voting decisions. Here the researchers considered a repetition of argumentation as a strong mechanism of influencing the voters' perception and decision-making process.

Similarly, L. Zhang & Min, (2013) examined the impacts of value framing on supporting gay rights in China. The researchers used experimental approach and divided the respondents into two groups for qualitative interview. Findings affirmed that, media widely used value framing strongly influenced the respondents' perceptions. The participants who watched gay rights-based documentaries showed a comparatively more positive attitude towards supporting LGBT rights. However, people who experienced watching the content attributing homosexuality to a matter of choice showed hostility and unacceptance towards acknowledging gays as equal and respectable in China.

Now the popular question is why mass media represent the political parties the way they do? Framing the elections is common among media platforms as they transfer the salience of a particular matter or a political party, which further helps the voters make a decision. Here sometimes, framing also undermines the normative functions of media regarding public wellbeing (Schuck et al., 2013). For instance, News media often focuses more on reporting the issue under game or conflict frames. Politicians use these frames to attribute negativity to their rivals and affect their reputations (Pedersen, 2014). To further validate this, Pedersen, (2014) examined negative campaigning along-with strategic frames during elections and their potential impacts on voting decisions. The researcher selected a literature review approach by randomly selecting published research articles. Results revealed that negative campaigning strongly influenced people's opinions and voting decisions. The researchers concluded that negative framing is comparatively more influential than positive framing due to attractive media content and strategies during elections.

From same-sex marriage to other public well-fare laws, people's voting decisions highly rely upon their personal experiences, perceptions, and opinions. When media focus more on public wellbeing, frames become comparatively more influential on voters' decisions. For this purpose, media platforms largely address the complex issues and represent them in easily understandable frames, which directly influence the voters' decision-making during elections (Hastings & Cannn, 2014). Furthermore, Waheed et al., (2015) examined the mediating role of values and media framing during elections. The researchers used a cross-sectional study design and selected a sample of $n= 337$ respondents from the Netherlands. Results revealed that people who believed more in universalism were more influenced by media framing than conservatives or strictly

following their cultural values. The findings affirmed the research hypotheses assume the role of culture as a primary determinant of framing influences.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Despite political framing and partial representations, the role of media reporting is highly acknowledged. As journalists support and practice freedom of expression and information, the electoral process becomes more transparent. This political coverage transparency motivates people to stay informed and vote for their desired candidates (Association for Progressive Communication, 2020). Besides, reinforcing political participation requires engaging the public in political activities. For traditional methods of supporting political participation through conventional media platforms, contemporary trends in communication also play a significant role (Geise et al., 2020).

Thus, the cited literature in the current research also revealed that, news media coverage regarding political communication and information increases the possibilities of voters' turnover. Here, the assumptions are that the more people stay updated about the elections, the more they vote (Bursztyn et al., 2018). Today with the higher reliance on mass media, people take a special interest in obtaining political information. Both new and traditional media platforms are equally preferred for everyone that help them to participate in elections. Thus there is a clear link between political information and voting behavior as media bridge the correlation between these two (Wolfsfeld et al., 2016). Notably, there are six primary ways the news media affect both elections and voters' political engagement, such as the polarization of media platforms, through pictures and video content, interacting directly with the public, watchdog of the democratic process by continuously checking the polling stations and any potential conflicts between the political parties and politicians. In this manner, presenting the political stories during the elections increases participation and strengthened the democratic system.

Likewise, framing is widely used when analyzing the media effect investigating the role of media and other external and internal factors on people's perceptions and attitudes. The role of traditional and new media work hand in hand as the audience considers traditional media platforms more preferable and reliable. News media's strong assistance, repetition of information, repeated exposure, and biased content all work collectively to influence the political decision-making process (Cacciatore et al., 2016). In this regard, Wettstein & Wirth, (2017) described media effects in a two-step process. First, media content influences the acquisition of more information on a political phenomenon. In the second step, acquired media information is accompanied by emotional and attitudinal reactions, which lead to making the relevant voting decisions. Both framing and agenda-setting work hand in hand to captivate the audience's attention and influence their decision-making process as political persuasion is common during elections and routine life functions. Political goals and objectives are the dynamics of media framing and strategic media proceedings that contain the particular type of persuasive message, its content, and timing. Partisan

politics also influence the media stakeholders to convey the desired political information and benefit from financial and others (Leeper & Slothuus, 2018).

Hence, from the early day of mass media research, media platforms have been considered a source of information and communication for the audience. Earlier, the emphasis was merely on the radio and television, however gradually, with the expansion of mass media research, print media also became a center of attention. Here Groombridge argued that medium is a prominent component of civilizing our "arid communal existence." Media platforms have a major contribution in highlighting several social-economic and political phenomena. In this context, political communication is a prominent part of media content that strengthens democracy (Gurevitch et al., 2009). The role of media in a democracy is not merely speculation, as early studies also witnessed the mass media in representing the political facts, their framing, and their influences on voters' voting engagement and decision-making process (Rexha, 2014). Previous studies conducted by Gérard, (1969) Harlan, (1970), and Blumler, (1979) were pioneering evidence that provided a pathway to media research in political communication and its perceived impacts. Therefore, by keeping the underlying facts of political communication, media coverage of elections, and impacts, the current study also provides in-depth insights regarding the media and politics, especially during the elections.

4.1 Limitations & Recommendations:

Despite this study containing an extensive data review, yet it also contains two primary limitations. **First** we did not focus on any particular media platform (traditional/conventional) regarding their role to influence the voters' engagement and decision-making process. **Second**, we have selected a limited number of study, whereas the role of media in voting process is highlighted and interrogated by a massive number of studies. Thus, we have carefully gathered and analyzed the data and recommend empirical research on the role of news media in voting process, to further examine the in-depth details in terms of media framing and political participation.

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